

Fruity expression of red wines resulting from varieties adapted to climate change. A comparative study with the "traditional" grape varieties planted in Bordeaux

JUSTINE GARBAY, Margaux Cameleyre, Nicolas Le Menn, Jean-Christophe Barbe and Georgia Lytra

Unité de recherche OEnologie, EA 4577, USC 1366 INRAE, ISVV, Université de Bordeaux, F33882 Villenave d'Ornon France, justine.garbay@u-bordeaux.fr

Abstract

Currently, one of the major issues for the wine sector is the impact of climate change linked to the increasing temperatures recorded and expected in the upcoming years. The vegetative cycle of the grape varieties authorised and planted in the Bordeaux wine region is tending to shorten, affecting the physicochemical parameters of the grapes and, consequently, the quality of the wines. In some varieties, the attenuation of their fresh fruity character is accompanied by the accentuation of dried-fruit notes [1]. As of today, winegrowers must implement adaptive strategies to continue producing high quality wines in a climate that is becoming warmer and drier. Some winegrowers have initiated changes in the mix of vine varieties [2].

This study intends to explore the fruitiness in wines produced from grape varieties adapted to the future climate of Bordeaux. Indeed, Bordeaux wines currently have a recognized fruity typicity [3], that it is imperative to preserve to maintain its reputation and avoid economic and, therefore social consequences.

For that, commercial single-variety wines from 2018 vintage made from the main grape varieties grown in the Bordeaux region (Merlot and Cabernet-Sauvignon) as well as from indigenous grape late-ripening varieties from the Mediterranean basin were collected, such as France (Cabernet-Franc, Cabernet-Sauvignon, Merlot and Syrah), Greece (Agiorgitiko, Xinomavro), Portugal (Touriga Nacional) and Spain (Garnacha and Tempranillo). Wines were evaluated sensorially: a sorting task was instructed to the panel and descriptive analyses of all wines were recorded with descriptors related to the fruity character of each wine. To study their fruity aroma expression, samples were prepared from wine, using an HPLC method which preserves wine aroma and isolates fruity characteristics in 25 specific fractions [3]. A trained panel evaluated sensorially the fractions. The descriptors characterising each wine matched those attributed to the different fractions. Then all fractions with intense fruity notes were selected for each wine and the comparative study of their fruity expression highlighted some fractions of interest. Aromatic reconstitutions were realised by mixing fractions with a fruity aroma ("fruity pool") in ethanol and microfiltered water to obtain an ethanol level of 12% (v/v). By comparing the fruity expression of each fruity aromatic reconstitution (FAR) made from the different late-grape varieties previously selected, 3 distinct groups were highlighted. FAR of wines made from late-grape varieties from Spain (Garnacha and Tempranillo) were gathered into the group 1 with the FAR of the wine made from a grape variety from France (Syrah). The group 1 was characterised by "red-berry", "black-berry" and "exotic" fruits notes. The group 2 was composed by FARs of wines made from two grape-varieties from France (Cabernet-Sauvignon and Merlot) and two grape-varieties from Greece (Agiorgitiko and Xinomavro). This second group was mainly described as "red-berry", "black-berry", "candy", "amylic" and "artificial" fruits notes. Finally, FAR of the wine made from grape variety from Portugal (Touriga Nacional) was classified into the group 3 with the FAR of the wine made from the last grape variety from France (Cabernet-Franc). The group 3 was mainly characterised by "freshness", "mint" and "eucalyptus" notes.

These results open up new prospects for the preparation of aromatic reconstitutions [4] from several fractions in order to study the impact of perceptive interactions on wine fruity aroma expression after the integration of wines from "new" late-ripening varieties in Bordeaux blends.

Keywords: red wine, fruity notes, fractionation, climate change, late-ripening varieties

Introduction

In the Bordeaux vineyards, the climatic conditions of recent vintages have led to a great heterogeneity in grape ripening. Various parameters, such as the variety mix, have affected the wines' aromatic expression. These climatic variations have resulted in higher quality wines made from late-ripening varieties, such as Cabernet-Sauvignon. From a sensory standpoint, oenologists have noted a strong influence of climate change on the aromatic quality and typicality of red wines. Among the multiple sensory characteristics involved in judging wine quality, olfactory notes are the most affected [5]. Thus, today, the fruity character of red wines, typical of a particular region, is considered synonymous with quality and highly sought-after by consumers. The work of Pineau [3] highlighted the existence of a fruity aroma, specific to Bordeaux red wines, marked by notes of "black-berry" and "jammy" fruit. Therefore, adapting the variety mix by (re-)introducing more suitable, late-ripening varieties seems essential to avoid a radical change in the fruity expression of Bordeaux wines [2].

Climate change is tending towards warmer, drier conditions, increasing the risk that, in the medium term, grape varieties that currently produce satisfactory results in the various production regions, and more precisely Merlot, will no longer be adapted in the future. Therefore, it makes sense to research the possibility of modifying the blend and (re-)introducing grape varieties adapted to the future climate. In order to preserve the fruity typicality of Bordeaux region wines after the introduction of these “new” grape varieties in the vineyards, the sector wishes to evaluate their aromatic potential by comparing them to the main grape varieties currently grown in the Bordeaux region (Merlot, Cabernet-Sauvignon, and Cabernet franc). The aim is to evaluate wines made from indigenous grape varieties from the Mediterranean basin (France, Greece, Italy, Spain, Portugal, etc.) planted in areas with hot climates (simulating the future climate of Bordeaux), and compare them with wines made from the main grape varieties currently grown in the Bordeaux region.

Experimental

Acquisition of wines

Nineteen commercial single-varietal red wines made from late-ripening grape varieties planted in a region with a high-temperature climate (Mediterranean basin) were collected (Table 1). These wines were from the 2018 vintage, as red wines express their typical fruity aroma, distinguishable from the fermentation aromas, after at least 2 years of ageing [6].

Table 1: 19 commercial single-varietal red wines collected from the Mediterranean basin.

Country	Grape varieties
France	Cabernet franc, Cabernet-Sauvignon, Carmenere, Cinsault, Malbec, Merlot, Sciaccarello and Syrah
Greece	Agiorgitiko, Kotsifali and Xinomavro
Cyprus	Giannoudi and Mavro
Italy	Aglianico and Nebbiolo
Portugal	Touriga Nacional
Spain	Garnacha and Tempranillo

The aromatic properties of all the red wines were established using a sensory analysis methodology, exclusively via orthonasal perception. Wines were evaluated at the controlled room temperature (20 °C) of ISVV, in individual booths, using covered ISO glasses (ISO 3591:1977, 1977) containing about 50 mL liquid, coded with three-digit random numbers.

The panel consisted of five judges from the research laboratory staff at ISVV, Bordeaux University, and all experts in assessing fruity aromas in red wines. Two questions were addressed to the panel to evaluate the fruity aromatic quality of each of the presented wines: “Does this wine have one or more defects? If yes, please specify which defect(s) you have detected” and “Among the wines sorted as “defect-free wines”, please perform a generation of descriptors (maximum 5) related to the fruitiness of the wine (if fruitiness is perceived)”. This acquisition phase consisted of discussing the fruity characteristic descriptors for the whole panel (NF ISO 11035: 1995) and selecting the wines with qualitative fruity descriptors, marked by black-berry, red-berry, fresh and jammy fruit notes and excluding those with dried-fruit notes.

Realisation of Aromatic Reconstitutions (AR)

Samples were prepared from 9 single-varietal red wines, using a methodology optimised by Lytra et al. [4]. A 500 mL wine sample was extracted successively using 80, 80 and 40 mL of dichloromethane, with a separatory funnel for 10 min. The organic phases were collected, blended, dried over sodium sulphate, and concentrated under nitrogen flow (100 mL/min) to obtain 1.25 mL of wine extract. Aroma extract of wines were eluted with a Reversed-Phase (RP) High-Performance-Liquid-Chromatography (HPLC) methodology, developed by Ferreira et al. [7]. The HPLC fractionation was realised by using a Nova-Pak C18 column (300 × 3.9 mm i.d., 4 µm, 60 Å, Waters, Saint-Quentin, France), without a guard cartridge [3]. The HPLC system consisted of an L-6200A pump (Merck-Hitachi, Germany). Chromatographic conditions were as optimised by Pineau [3]: 20 flow rate, 0.5 mL/min; injection volume, 250 µL wine extract; program gradient, phase A, water, phase B, ethanol; 0–2 min, 100% A, linearly programmed until 100% B at minute 50. The effluent was collected in 1 mL fractions.

This methodology was used to isolate fractions with intense fruity notes (fractions 17–21), thus creating a fruity pool. For fruity AR (FAR), fractions of the fruity pool (fractions 17-21) were blended together to reproduce the initial concentrations in the original wines, adding ethanol and microfiltered water to obtain an ethanol level of 12% (v/v) [4].

Sensory analysis of Aromatic Reconstitutions

Nine FAR were all presented randomly to the panel to compare the fruitiness of samples. A free sorting task was applied to explore perceptive similarities among FAR [8]. Assessors were instructed to classify each FAR according to their similarities or dissimilarities. No constraints were required for this test and assessors had the possibility to do the number of groups they wanted (with the minimum of 2 groups) and to put as many samples they considered important into each group. Then, participants were asked to generate some descriptors to describe each group.

Results and discussion

Acquisition of wines

Three wines that presented aromatic defects (notes of reduction, vegetal and horsy notes) were eliminated. Sixteen wines were characterised as “defect-free wines”, but 8 of them were marked by a non-typical fruit (dried fruit notes). Finally, 8 wines described with a typical fruit (red-berry, black berry, fresh and jammy fruit notes) were collected for this study. The single-varietal red wines presenting the most qualitative typical fruity aroma were: Garnacha (Spain), Tempranillo (Spain), Touriga Nacional (Portugal), Xinomavro (Greece), Agiorgitiko (Greece), Cabernet-Franc (France), Cabernet-Sauvignon (France) and Syrah (France). The Merlot wine (from France) was kept for further analysis, even if its fruity character was not typical, with the aim to compare its fruity expression to the fruity expression of other single-varietal wines.

Data collection and analysis: Free sorting task test

A total of 25 fractions (fractions 1-25) with various flavours were obtained and evaluated by the panel using a free sorting task test. The descriptors characterising each wine matched those attributed to the different fractions and the fruity character of each selected wine (marked by black-berry, red-berry, fresh and jammy fruits) was preserved into the fruity pool (fractions 17-21).

Data collected from the free sorting task test were organised into a dissimilarity matrix (Table 2) [9]. Then, a Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was performed on the dissimilarity matrix to obtain a dendrogram (Figure 1). Samples were gathered according to their similarities or dissimilarities comparing their fruity expression.

Statistical analysis highlighted the existence of 3 distinct groups constituted by different FAR made from different single-varietal red wines (Figure 1). The first group in green colour was composed by the FAR of the two single-varietal red wines from Spain, Garnacha (A) and Tempranillo (B), and the single-varietal red wine from France, Syrah (G). Regarding the second group in orange colour, FAR of the two grape varieties from France, Cabernet-Sauvignon (E) and Merlot (I), were classified with the FAR of the two grape varieties from Greece, Xinomavro (C) and Agiorgitiko (D). Finally, the third group in violet colour was composed by the single-varietal red wines from France, Cabernet-Franc (F) and from Portugal, Touriga Nacional (H).

Table 2: Dissimilarity matrix on data generated by the free sorting task test (A: Garnacha; B: Tempranillo; C: Xinomavro; D: Agiorgitiko; E: Cabernet-Sauvignon; F: Cabernet-Franc; G: Syrah; H: Touriga Nacional; I: Merlot).

	AR - A	AR - B	AR - C	AR - D	AR - E	AR - F	AR - G	AR - H	AR - I
AR - A	0	4	3	4	5	5	2	3	3
AR - B	4	0	5	5	4	4	3	5	4
AR - C	3	5	0	3	4	4	4	3	4
AR - D	4	5	3	0	3	5	5	4	3
AR - E	5	4	4	3	0	4	5	5	4
AR - F	5	4	4	5	4	0	5	2	5
AR - G	2	3	4	5	5	5	0	4	5
AR - H	3	5	3	4	5	2	4	0	4
AR - I	3	4	4	3	4	5	5	4	0

Figure 1: Dendrogram obtained using a dissimilarity matrix applied on free sorting data (A: Garnacha; B: Tempranillo; C: Xinomavro; D: Agiorgitiko; E: Cabernet-Sauvignon; F: Cabernet-Franc; G: Syrah; H: Touriga Nacional; I: Merlot).

Data collection and analysis: Generation of descriptors based on citation frequencies

Ten descriptors were generated by the panel, and were gathered into 5 groups according to their olfactory similarities: “black-berry and red-berry fruits”, “exotic fruits”, “mint, eucalyptus and freshness notes”, “spicy” and “candy, amylic and dark fruits”. The citation frequency of descriptors for each group was calculated using the number of time a word is cited in each group divided by the total number of time the word is cited.

Citations frequencies of various descriptors for each group were represented on a histogram (Figure 2). Participants selected “black-berry” and “red-berry” descriptors for all the 3 groups with a higher citation frequency for the group 2, composed by FAR from the 2 single-varietal red wines from Greece (Agiorgitiko and Xinomavro) and from France (Cabernet-Sauvignon and Merlot).

The first group was mainly characterised by “black-berry”, “red-berry” and “exotic” fruits. The second group was mainly characterised by “candy, amylic, artificial fruits” and “spicy” notes, as well as “exotic”, “black-berry and red-berry” fruits. Finally, the third group was mainly described as “mint, eucalyptus and freshness” notes, as well as “exotic”, “black-berry” and “red-berry” fruits.

Figure 2: Histogram obtained using citation frequencies of each generated descriptors (Group 1: Garnacha, Tempranillo, Syrah; Group 2: Cabernet-Sauvignon, Merlot, Agiorgitiko, Xinomavro; Group 3: Cabernet-Franc and Touriga Nacional).

Conclusion

Qualitative descriptors, marked by “black-berry” and “red-berry” fruits, were found in several single-varietal red wines made from late-grape varieties from the Mediterranean basin, opening perspectives for their addition to Bordeaux traditional blend. Different groups of similarity were formed. FAR of Cabernet-Sauvignon, Merlot, Agiorgitiko and Xinomavro were gathered together, highlighting their similar fruitiness and the possible replacement of Merlot by these varieties in the Bordeaux traditional blend. The aromatic reconstitution of the “fruity pool” of Merlot red wine was finally characterised with a qualitative fruity expression suggesting that the fruity character of the overall aroma of Merlot red wines may be affected by other compounds in wine.

As a future perspective, sensory analyses will be coupled with instrumental analysis to understand how aromatic composition and variation of some compounds may influence the fruity expression in samples. Moreover, investigating new perceptual interactions due to the presence of some aroma compounds responsible for the mint and freshness notes in FAR, remains an interesting study. Further sensory analyses need to be performed to extend and validate these results using other experimental conditions such as panel, wine references, grape-varieties diversity and wine vintage.

References

1. Pons A, Allamy L, Schüttler A, Rauhut D, Thibon C, Darriet P. What is the expected impact of climate change on wine aroma compounds and their precursors in grape? *OENO One*. 2017;51(2):141-146.
2. Van Leeuwen C, Destruct-Irvine A, Dubernet M, Duchêne E, Gowdy M, Marguerit E, Ollat N. An update on the impact of climate change in viticulture and potential adaptations. *Agronomy*. 2019;9(9):514.
3. Pineau B. Contribution à l'étude de l'arôme fruité spécifique des vins rouges de *Vitis vinifera* L. cv. Merlot noir et Cabernet-Sauvignon. Ph.D. Thesis. 2007, University of Bordeaux 2.
4. Lytra G, Tempere S, De Revel G, Barbe J.C. Impact of perceptible interactions on red wine fruity aroma. *J. Agric. Food Chem*. 2012;60(50):12260-12269.
5. Van Leeuwen C, Barbe J.C., Darriet P, Gomès E, Guillaumie S, Thibon C. Recent advancements in understanding the terroir effect on aromas on aromas in grapes and wines. *OENO One*. 2020;54(4):985-1006.
6. Lytra G, Franc C, Cameleyre M, Barbe J.C. Study of substituted ester formation in red wine by the development of a new method for quantitative determination and enantiomeric separation of their corresponding acids. *J. Agric. Food Chem*. 2017;65(24):5018-5025.
7. Ferreira V, Hernandez-Orte P, Escudero A, Lopez R, Cacho J. Semipreparative reversed-phase liquid chromatographic fractionation of aroma extracts from wine and other beverages. *J. Chromatogr., A*. 1999;864:77-88.
8. Maître I, Symoneaux R, Jourjon F, Mehinagic E. Sensory typicality of wines: How scientists have recently dealt with this subject. *Food Qual. Prefer*. 2010;21:726-731.
9. Faye P, Courcoux P, Qannari E.M., Giboreau A. Méthodes de traitement statistique des données issues d'une épreuve de tri libre. *Revue MODULAD*. 2011;43.